

Research Article

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Farmers as Correlates of Fertilizer Demand in Ekiti State, Southwest Nigeria: Implications for Agricultural Extension

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ABSTRACT

The importance of inorganic fertilizer to farmers is without doubt. This is because of the overriding effect on increased crop yield. This study examines the influence of farmers' socioeconomic characteristics on fertilizer demand in Ekiti State, Southwest Nigeria. Data were collected from 124 randomly selected respondents in the study area. Data analysis revealed that fertilizer demand was low generally per hectare and there was attendant price fluctuation of bags of fertilizer in the study area. The regression analysis revealed that farmer status, farming experience, age, educational level, marital status, household size, farm size, income, and land ownership significantly correlated with fertilizer demand among farmers in Ekiti State, Southwestern Nigeria. It was recommended that adequate awareness should be created by the State Agricultural Development Programme to generate interest of the farmers towards the use of fertilizer for enhanced yield and productivity. Efforts should also be made to reduce the Extension-farmer ratio so that a reasonable number of farmers can be reached with improved practice.

Key words: Fertilizer consumption, farmers, Ekiti State, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the mainstay of Nigeria's economy. Recently, because of the economic reforms, Nigeria is gradually moving towards self sufficiency in food production. In order to sustain this self sufficiency tempo, the management of soil resources cannot be overemphasized. Most part of southwestern Nigeria lies within the tropical rainforest (Guinea Savanna). The areas are characterized by climatic factors which include high relative humidity, torrential rainfall and high temperatures which jointly have a limiting effect on soil fertility of the lands that are available for agriculture (Pritchett and Fisher, 1987; Shodeke et al., 2006). Because of the substantial nutrient removal from soil by the various crops, it requires among other things, artificial fertilizers to keep pace with this loss (Olayide, 1981). One of the most effective ways of raising agricultural productivity according to (Abe, 1989) is through the application of fertilizers.

It has been observed (Falusi, 1989) that fertilizers are important for the savannah zones because annual bush burning destroys the organic matter and thus makes the soils poorer. However, it was noted, the steady price increase of fertilizer is making it increasingly difficult for individual small-scale farmers to buy the minimum 50kg pack. From the farmers' angle, fertilizer is needed to achieve higher production to meet increasing demand for food and other agricultural products (Amalu, 1998). In recent years, there has been a sharp rise in the use of fertilizers in Nigeria. In spite of the increase, Nigeria's per hectare use of fertilizers is very low. The estimated 9.4kg of nutrients per ha in 1986 is just 10% of the world's average and 18% of Kenya's consumption. Accordingly, the soils in Africa are no less crucial than climate (Oboh and Nzenwa, 2005). Soil fertility issues, particularly in the humid tropics are of importance to rural people and farmers in developing countries. In the past, the agricultural system in Nigeria relied on shifting cultivation to maintain soil fertility through organic and plant nutrient buildup during fallows (Abu, 2002). Due to population pressure, decreased urbanization, marginal land is gradually being brought under cultivation while fallow periods have reduced (Tanko and Mbanasor, 2000). As a result of this, the importance of fertilizer for accelerated agricultural production in Nigeria is without doubt.

However, (Babatunde and Boluwade, 2004) noted that one major problem here is high cost and unavailability of fertilizer which forced government to subsidize the product. The subsidy scenario has unfortunately been very inconsistent. Ekiti State is a food basket in southwestern Nigeria known for the production of major staple crops. It is therefore expected that since these crops are grown regularly, nutrient supplements are required to replenish the lost soil nutrients. However, the nature of fertilizer consumption among farmers is not certain. This study therefore ascertains the inorganic fertilizer consumption trend (2001-2005). The study also identifies socio-economic characteristics of farmers and their perceived impact of fertilizer application.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Ekiti state, Southwestern Nigeria. Nine local government areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from the 16 in the state. They include Ikole, Ekiti East, Efon, Ado, Ikere, Moba, Ekiti West, Ijero and Irepodun/Ifelodun. From these LGAs, two communities were randomly selected and from the communities, seven respondents were randomly chosen with the help of the State ADP Extension Agents. In all 126 respondents were involved in the study but data were available from 124 respondents which made up the sample used for the study.

Ekiti State enjoys tropical climate which has the wet and dry seasons. Mean annual temperature ranges between 21°C to 28°C and mean annual rainfall ranges between 1200mm to 1800mm. For the purpose of agricultural planning, Ekiti State is strategically divided into 2 agro-ecological zones, northern savannah and southern forest zones. The study covered the two zones. The major crops grown include maize, rice, cocoa, cassava, cocoyam, tomatoes, pepper, okra, yam, potatoes, beans, plantain, banana, oil palm, citrus. Ekiti soil is essentially of basement complex origin (Shodeke et al., 2006).

Data for the study were collected with the aid of a questionnaire in an open and closed ended format. Data analysis was by frequency, percentage and Ordinary Least Square multiple regression.

Analytical technique

To determine the relationship between socio-economic characteristics of respondents and their fertilizer consumption, the regression model was specified thus:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, X_9, X_{10}, X_{11}, e)$$

Where

Y	=	Fertilizer consumption (bags)
X ₁	=	Gender (Male= 2, female = 1)
X ₂	=	Farmer status (fulltime = 2, Part-time = 1)
X ₃	=	Primary occupation (Farming = 1, Civil service = 2, trading = 3, none = 4)
X ₄	=	Experience in farming (years)
X ₅	=	Age (years)
X ₆	=	Education (years in school)
X ₇	=	Marital status (Married = 2= single =1)
X ₈	=	Household size (number of persons)
X ₉	=	Farm size (hectares)
X ₁₀	=	Annual income (Naira)
X ₁₁	=	Farm ownership (Personal = 1, family = 2, lease = 3)
e	=	The error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents

The results from table 1 showed that majority of the respondents were male (83.9%), and operated on part time basis (50.8%). Also, a moderate percentage of the respondents were civil servants (36.2%), while a greater proportion were farmers (49.2%). Findings showed that respondents had farming experience of 22years on the average, and the mean age of respondents was 45years. Also 41.95% of the respondents were educated up to secondary level and 88.7% were married. Ownership status of land was found to be with the family (40.3%). The average annual income was ₦145, 282. A significant percentage of the respondents (54%) had farm size ranging from 0.5 to 2ha. Household size ranged from 3-7 members (54.8%). A significant percentage of the respondents (61.3%) got their fertilizer supply from the state Agricultural Development Programme (ADP). It was

found that 76.6% of the respondents applied fertilizer to their crops and experienced significant impact on their crop yield (73.4%).

Table 1: socio-economic characteristics of respondents (n =124)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	104	83.9
Female	20	16.1
Farmer status		
Full time	61	49.2
Part time	63	50.8
Primary occupation		
Farming	61	49.2
Civil service	45	36.3
Trading	15	12.1
None	3	2.4
Farming experience		
5-15years	46	37.1
16-25years	39	31.5
26-35years	21	16.9
Above 35years	18	14.5
Age		
20-30years	25	20.2
31-40years	18	14.5
41-50years	48	38.7
51-60years	13	10.5
Above 60years	20	16.1
Education		
Primary	24	19.4
Secondary	52	41.9
Tertiary	48	38.7
Marital status		
Married	110	88.7
Single	14	11.3
Land ownership		
Personal	28	22.6
Family	50	40.3
Lease	46	37.1
Annual income (Naira)		
10, 000-50,000	19	15.3
51, 000-90, 000	27	21.8
91, 000-130, 000	33	26.6
131, 000-170, 000	15	12.1
171, 000 and above	30	24.2
Farm size (ha)		
0.5 -2	67	54.0
2.5 – 4	38	31.0
4.5 – 7.5	12	10.0
Above 7.5	7	5.0
Household size		
0	14	11.3
3-7	68	54.8
8-12	33	26.7
13-16	9	7.2
Source of fertilizer supply		
No response	44	35.5
ADP	76	61.3
Open market	4	3.2
Do you apply fertilizers?		
Yes	95	76.6
No	29	23.4

*Multiple response

Source: Field survey 2006

Reasons for not applying fertilizers

As to why some did not apply fertilizer at all or why they have not been applying it on a continuous basis, there were multiple answers as can be observed in Figure 1. About 10% of the respondents indicated that it makes no difference whether they applied fertilizers or not, 24.2% indicated that it is too costly, 6.9% indicated that it is forbidden. Also, 27.6% of the respondents indicated that it is not easily available, 17.2% indicated that their land is already fertile, while 13.8% indicated that applying fertilizer will affect the taste of produce.

Quantity and price of fertilizer purchased

From Table 2, there was a rise in quantity of fertilizer purchased by farmers from 2 bags to a peak of an average of 3 bags per farmer in 2005. Also price of fertilizer was ₦1, 450 in 2001 and dropped in 2002. However price increase rose from 2003 up till 2005. The corresponding rise in quantity suggests that respondents appreciate the importance of fertilizer to crop production. Ekiti State is a food basket that boasts of significant crops like rice, yam, cassava, cocoyam, banana, potatoes and cowpea while tree crops like cocoa, colanut, Oil Palm, citrus, also thrive.

There is no doubt that there is a steady growth in fertilizer use in Nigeria. Despite the steady growth, the rate of fertilizer consumption per hectare in Nigeria ranks among the lowest in the world (Ogunfowora, 1989). It has been reported that at the initial stage of introduction of fertilizer into the country, the use levels were moderate. However, in more recent times the quantity consumed rose from 118, 586 tons of product in 1975 to 673, 000 tons in 1987 (Wedderburn, 1989).

The high cost of fertilizers has been a major constraint to its use. It is however, worse during times of scarcity. For instance, it was reported (Wedderburn, 1989) that in times of scarcity, illegal markets flourish where fertilizer retail prices could be four times the official price. In spite of that, farmers are still willing to buy at such prices. The cost of fertilizer constitutes a serious obstacle to farmers (Obasi et al., 2005). On the part of government, the foreign exchange needed for imports, building and maintenance of fertilizer factories is an equally serious problem. In a study on fertilizer procurement (Obasi et al., 2005) distribution and subsidy policies in Nigeria found that South West Nigeria got 3, 660 metric tons of fertilizer out of the total 96, 148 metric tons across the 6 geographic zones. This represented a paltry 6%. In terms of the trends in quality of fertilizers

demanded in Nigeria, it was revealed that the quantity demanded declined from 987, 500 metric tons in 1985 to 34, 000 tons in 1988. It then rose steadily to 934, 000 tons in 1993, and declined to 60, 150 tons in 1997. The quantity rose from 101, 149 tons in 1999 to 946, 798 tons in 2001, representing an increase of about 89%. The erratic trend in the quantities of fertilizers demanded over the years has been blamed on inconsistent government policies (Njoku, 2005). The variations reported in fertilizer prices from 1996 showed that the price dropped from N1, 350 to N1, 035 in 1999 and rose to N1, 240.

Table 2: Average quantity and price of fertilizer purchased

Year	Quantity (bags)	Price bought (₦)
2001	2	1, 450
2002	1.5	1, 050
2003	2	1, 110
2004	3	1, 250
2005	2	1, 300
Average	2.1	1, 232

Source: Field survey 2006

Table 3: regression analysis showing relationship between fertilizer consumption and socioeconomic characteristics of farmers

Variables	Linear	Semilog	Double log	Exponential log
Constant	-53.400 (-4.955)	-81.910 (-3.939)	-3.640 (-1.725)	-5.135 (-5.230)
Gender	1.156 (0.467)	1.934 (0.532)	0.478 (1.295)	0.291 (1.150)
Farmer status	8.850 (1.976)**	7.248 (1.740)***	0.783 (1.852)***	0.750 (2.517)**
Occupation	1.111 (0.475)	-1.003 (-0.249)	-0.250 (-0.610)	1.923E-02 (0.081)
Farming experience	-0.461 (-2.799) *	-7.060 (-2.731)*	-0.680 (-2.593) **	-2.783E-02 (-1.655) ***
Age	0.382 (2.619) *	15.255 (2.553) **	0.980 (1.616) *	8.809E-03 (0.591)
Education	4.591 (2.638) *	9.666 (2.988) *	1.465 (4.464)	0.736 (4.145) **
Marital status	7.624 (1.983) **	12.292 (1.404)	3.350 (3.773) **	1.656 (4.386) **
Household size	-0.744 (-1.771) ***	-4.440 (-1.159)	-0.837 (-2.154) **	-0.110 (-2.562) **
Farm size	1.840 (5.185) *	7.686 (4.933) ***	0.571 (3.615) **	0.127 (3.497) **
Income	1.207E-05 (1.655) ***	2.663 (2.126) **	1.911E-02 (0.150)	-7.737E-07 (-0.988)
Farm ownership	5.714 (3.268) *	9.639 (2.854) **	0.704 (2.056)**	0.407 (2.279) **
R ²	0.598	0.457	0.541	0.552
F	10.118	8.579	12.014	12.552
N	124	124	124	124

* Significant at 1% level; ** Significant at 5% level; *** Significant at 10% level

Source: Field Survey, 2006.

Relationship between fertilizer consumption and socioeconomic characteristics of farmers

The regression results as shown in table 3 reveals that 9 out of the 11 variables significantly influenced fertilizer demand. In the linear functional form which provided the lead equation out of the four different equations, the 9 variables accounted for about 59.8% of the variance in the model. Farmer status positively and significantly influenced fertilizer demand ($t=1.976$; $P<0.05$). The implication of this finding is that part-time farmers demanded more fertilizers for the farm crops. Farming experience negatively but significantly influenced fertilizer demand ($t=-2.799$, $P<0.05$), suggesting that respondents with less years of farming experience demanded more fertilizers for their crops. This is not unexpected because they may not want to take undue risks on their yield.

Age of respondents positively and significantly influenced fertilizer demand ($t=2.619$; $P<0.01$), implying that older respondents demanded more fertilizer while younger farmers demanded less fertilizers for their crops.

This is contrary to the *a priori* as younger people have been found to adopt innovation more easily than the older ones. Young farmers tend to be more flexible in their decisions, adopt new ideas more readily because of anticipated life span within which investment in new technology will pay off (Njoku, 2005). Education was positively and significantly related to fertilizer demand ($t=2.638$; $P<0.01$). This suggests that higher educational level influenced higher fertilizer demand and in line with previous study (Njoku, 2005) which reported that education correlates positively with adoption of improved practice. This is expected since most of the respondents in the study were educated. Marital status of respondents positively and significantly influenced fertilizer demand ($t=1.983$; $P<0.05$). The implication here is that married respondents demanded for fertilizer more than unmarried respondents since marital status of respondents represents some level of family responsibility, the need to grow more crops to feed more mouth will engender demand for fertilizer to be high.

Household size showed negative but significant relationship with fertilizer demand ($t=1.771$; $P<0.1$), suggesting that respondents with fewer persons in the household demanded more fertilizer. This is not in line with theoretical expectation because higher household members would require more food and this would mean more fertilizer to grow more quality crops. However, the present finding may not be unconnected to the fact that large household size was found in the study area with a maximum of 16 persons in a household. The average of 7 persons per household found may imply that they require more bags of fertilizers for their crops to do better.

Farm size was positive and significantly related to demand for fertilizer ($t=5.185$; $P<0.01$). The implication of this is that the larger the farm size, the higher the demand for fertilizer. Income of respondents positively and significantly influenced fertilizer demand ($t=1.207E-05$; $P<0.1$). This suggests that respondents with higher income demand for higher quantities of fertilizer, obviously because they can afford it. Land ownership ($t=3.268$; $P<0.01$) positively and significantly influenced fertilizer demand, implying that family ownership of farmland presupposes that more people will collectively demand for fertilizer.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The results as depicted gave the impression that the use of fertilizer among the farmers in Ekiti state is popular. However in terms of quantity being used and the expressed opinions of a good number of the respondents regarding their beliefs of natural fertility of the soil which makes fertilizer usage unnecessary, high cost and the difficulty encountered in getting it, the projected picture of a good adoption may be misleading. For instance, an average of 2 bags (100kg) of fertilizer usage per farmer, per annum is quite inadequate to bring forth an optimum harvest in 1 hectare of either maize, cassava or rice plot because for each of them, one would need up to four bags (200kg) at planting and another 100 – 200kg as a second dose depending on the area. In actual fact, most of the respondents were ADP farmers who despite the opportunity of contact with the Extension officers, still perform so low. It is also logical to infer that most of those who expressed negative responses did so because of the very high outreach family ratio of 1 : 1828. This is a great challenge.

Consequently, it is recommended that all avenues open to the ADP and the stakeholders be exploited to create awareness and generate interest of the farmers towards the use of fertilizer for enhanced yield and productivity. This could be strategized on broad – based farmer organizations rather than an *ad hoc* project-led groups characterized with the ADP system most often. This will stimulate a demand – pull for fertilizer usage by greater majority of the farmers who at present are not benefiting in any of the ADP projects.

In an effort to reach out to more farmers, the ADP should endeavour to reduce the Extension-farmers ratio from the present 1: 1828 to at least 1 : 1000, to cater for the estimated 128 000 farm families, if it is still difficult to meet the expected ratio of 1 : 800 through employment of new officers. Moreover, the government has a duty to ensure good subsidy and easy availability to the farmers. This will go a long way to enhance sustainable agricultural production.

REFERENCES

- Abe, J.O (1989) Fertilizer Promotion and Extension Prog- the ONADEP Experience. Towards better harvest for rural farmers. Proceedings 1st. Nation fertilizer workshop held in Durbar Hotel, Kaduna, June. 5-7
- Abu, O. (2002). Economic impact of fertilizer price on maize production in Nigeria (1976-1996) Unpublished MSc Thesis, Dept of Agric Econs, University of Agric, Makurdi.
- Amalu, U. (1998) *Agricultural research and Ext delivery systems in sub-Saharan Africa* Calabar: UNICAL Pres
- Babatunde, R.O, and E.O Boluwade (2004) Resource use efficiency in food crop production in Ekiti state Nigeria. *Journal of Agric and Social Research*, 4 (1), 105-117
- Enwezor, W.O. & A.W. Moore (1966). Phosphorus status of soil Nigeria soils. *Soil Sc.* 102: 322-328.
- Falusi, A.O (1989) fertilizer policy in the context of small holder Agricultural production in Nigeria Toward better harvest for rural farmers. *Proceedings of 1st National Fertilizer workshop held in Durbar Hotel, Kaduna, June. 5-7.*

- Matthews – Njoku, E.C (2005): Farmers adoption of improved soil conservation and management practice in a rainforest zone of Nigeria. Global approaches to Extension practice Vol. 1, 2005.
- Obasi, P.C., Dimkpa, T.R and Onyeka, U.P. (2005) Fertilizer procurement, distribution and subsidy policies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture and rural development*, 6, 58-65.
- Oboh, V.U. and G.C. Nzenwa (2005) fertilizer subsidy removal and its effects on maize production in Benue State. *Proceedings of the 39th conference of the Agric. Society of Nigeria*, Benin.
- Ogunfowora, B. (1989) Fertilizer outlook in Nigeria. Towards better harvest for rural farmers. Proceedings of the first fertilizer workshop held in Durbar Hotel, Kaduna, June 5-7.
- Olayide, S.O (1981) Food and Fibre production problems in rural setting. In: Olayide, S.O et al (eds) *Elements of rural economics*. Ibadan: Ibadan University Press publicity House.
- Pritchett, W.J. & R.F. Fisher (1987): *Properties & Management of forest soils 2nd ed.* John Wiley.
- Shodeke, D.K.A., G.O. Adeoye & A.A. Agboola (2006) Relationship between 4 inorganic phosphorus forms with regards to maize P uptake in 2 soils of south- western Nigeria. *Bowen J. of Agriculture*, 3 (1q), 38-48.
- Tanko, L. and J.A. Mbanasor (2000) Determinants of fertilizer demand in Kebbi State. *Journal of Agri-business and Rural development*, 1 (1), 74-78.
- Wedderburn, S. (1989) Cost-Benefit analysis of fertilizer use in Nigeria. Towards better harvest for rural farmers. Proceedings of the first fertilizer workshop held in Durbar Hotel, Kaduna, June 5-7.